

Global
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PROCEEDINGS

The 2nd GCC International Conference on Global Citizenship Education 2024

Building Inclusive Communities
Through Global Citizenship Education

6 - 8 August 2024

Universiti Sains Malaysia

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Universiti Sains Malaysia
Penang, Malaysia

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PREFACE

In 2015, the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) highlighted the importance of GCED through SDG 4.7. This goal underscores the necessity of education for sustainable development and global citizenship, aiming to ensure that learners acquire the knowledge and skills needed to promote sustainable development. The new UNESCO Recommendation in 2023 further reflects this inclusive concept, recognising Global Citizenship Education as one of the most essential education initiatives of our contemporary era.

These proceedings encapsulate the spirit of intellectual inquiry, the pursuit of knowledge, and the ceaseless quest that cover a wide range of topics, including curriculum development, pedagogical strategies, policy frameworks, and community engagement in GCED. Each contribution offers a unique lens through which we can deepen our understanding and promote understanding of diverse cultures, encourages critical thinking, and fosters the development of compassionate and active global citizens through education.

Moreover, the diverse range of methodologies, theories, and interdisciplinary perspectives showcased here highlights the dynamism and adaptability required to navigate the complexities of our globalized world and how new practices allow us to explore endless possibilities to overcome on-going challenges. It is a reminder that education plays a critical role in fostering a sense of shared humanity, mutual respect, and collective responsibility for our planet and its inhabitants.

Hence, Global Citizenship Education (GCED) aims to equip learners of all ages with the values, knowledge, and skills necessary to engage effectively and responsibly with the challenges and opportunities of our world. It is our goal to inspire and empower each person to take meaningful action in their own contexts, contributing to a more just, peaceful, and sustainable world.

On behalf of the GCCIC 2024 proceeding committee, we extend our deepest gratitude to all the contributors and reviewers whose dedication and passion have brought this compilation to fruition. We would also like to thank the Asia-Pacific Center of Education for International Understanding (APCEIU) under the auspices of UNESCO for fully funding this conference. Together, let us strive to build bridges across cultures and nations, to nurture empathy and understanding, and to empower the next generation of global citizens.

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GCCIC 2024 Proceeding

Global Citizenship Education: A Comparative All-Time Bibliometric Review of Asia and the Rest of the World in Scopus

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Introduction: Global citizenship education (GCE) has emerged as a crucial element in preparing individuals for the demands of an interconnected and interdependent world. Specifically, GCE aims to develop learners who can engage in global issues and contribute positively to society (Eis & Moulin-Doos, 2017). Its importance is underscored by its inclusion in frameworks like the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals, particularly Goal 4.7, which focuses on quality education that promotes global citizenship (Gardner-McTaggart & Palmer, 2018). However, the implementation and focus of GCE vary across regions. For example, Asia, with its diverse cultures, educational systems, and socio-political contexts (Vickers & Un, 2019), offers a unique perspective on GCE while other regions exhibit different trends and approaches. Understanding these regional variations is vital for educators, policymakers, and researchers aiming to enhance the effectiveness and reach of GCE worldwide. Previous bibliometric studies of GCE (e.g., Almohaimeed & Amzah, 2024) have focused on a global scope, often overlooking regional specifics. Bibliometric analysis provides valuable insights into publication trends, influential works, and research areas (Ellegaard & Wallin, 2015). Furthermore, leveraging comprehensive databases like Scopus allows researchers to uncover significant trends and patterns within GCE. **Purpose of study:** The purpose of this study is to conduct a detailed bibliometric analysis of global citizenship education (GCE) literature, comparing the scholarly output between Asia and the rest of the world in terms of publication and citation patterns as well as conceptual, intellectual, and social structure of GCE. By addressing these objectives, the study seeks to enhance the understanding of GCE's regional and global landscape and identify opportunities for furthering its impact through informed research and collaboration. **Methodology:** To conduct the bibliometric analysis of GCE, a search was performed using the Scopus database on August 1, 2024. The query string used was *TITLE-ABS-KEY("global citizen") AND (SUBJMAIN(3304))*. This string aimed to capture a broad range of literature related to GCE by targeting titles, abstracts, and keywords containing variations of the term "global citizen" and focusing on subject area 3304, which encompasses education. Conducted without language or year limitations, the search returned 1,438 records. From the retrieved dataset, documents classified as erratum and editorials were excluded, as well as those lacking authors' names, abstracts, and keywords. The dataset was refined using OpenRefine version 3.7.7 (Delpuch et al., 2023) to remove duplicates and irrelevant entries as well as to merge similar entries. The refined dataset was then analyzed using Bibliometrix via its web-based interface, Biblioshiny (Aria & Cuccurullo, 2017) with its default setting. The performance and network analyses involved a comparative examination of GCE research between Asia and the rest of the world. **Findings:** The first part of this section deals with the performance analysis of publication and citation patterns. Asia's GCE research began later than the rest of the world, starting in 2006 versus 2000. Despite this, Asia's output is growing rapidly, with 304 documents and a 22.74% annual growth rate, though it has a lower citation impact (10.36 citations per document) compared to the rest of the world, which has 871 documents, a 19.15% growth rate, and an average of 14.88 citations per document. Both regions share prominent sources, with Asia publishing 19 documents in *Globalisation, Societies and Education* and 12 in *Prospects*, while the rest of the world has 53 and 23 documents, respectively. Asia favors region-specific journals like *Asia Pacific Journal of Education*, while the rest of the world prefers international journals like *Journal of Studies in International Education*. In authorship, Yemini M leads in Asia with 14 articles, while Pashby K leads globally with 11 articles. The rest of the world's top authors show higher fractionalized counts, indicating greater

collaboration compared to their Asian counterparts. Asian authors demonstrate significant impact with high total citations and consistent h-indexes. Regarding institutional affiliations, the University of Hong Kong leads Asia with 68 articles, whereas Manchester Metropolitan University leads globally with 19 articles, reflecting a concentration of research in fewer Asian institutions compared to a broader range of contributors globally. The USA dominates with 28.76% of the documents outside Asia, while South Korea leads Asia with 13.22% of the region's production. Korea has the highest total citations in Asia (567), while the UK leads globally (3224). Although Asian studies show significant annual citation rates, global studies generally exhibit higher total and normalized citation counts, suggesting broader influence. Keywords analysis reveals both regions focus on "global citizenship" and "global citizenship education," but the rest of the world covers a wider range of topics with higher frequencies and earlier peaks compared to Asia. The second part of this section reports the results of network analyses in terms of the conceptual, intellectual, and social structure of knowledge. Conceptually, a network analysis of thematic evolution reveals show both regions prioritize transformative learning, sustainable development, and intercultural competence. Asia focuses on regional specifics and internationalization in higher education, while the rest of the world emphasizes psychological literacy, critical thinking, diversity, and global competencies. Intellectually, Andreotti V and Freire P are key figures in GCE for both regions, with Torres CA notably influential in Asia and Freire P prominent globally. Both regions share clusters in foundational topics and theoretical advancements, though emerging authors like Cho HS and Byker EJ have less central influence. Socially, the USA and the UK are central in both networks. Asia shows more regionally concentrated connections with China and Korea, while the rest of the world network is more dispersed, with strong European and American ties. The results suggest that bridging the gap between Asia and the rest of the world in GCE research requires a model integrating regional and global perspectives, fostering international collaboration, broadening thematic focus, and enhancing global visibility to improve citation impact and scholarly influence. **Discussions:** The findings indicate that while GCE research in Asia is expanding rapidly, it lags behind the rest of the world in citation impact and global reach. Asia's focus on regional issues and specific journals contrasts with the rest of the world's broader, more inclusive approach. The network analysis reveals that Asia is more regionally concentrated with key players like China and Korea, while global collaboration is more widespread, particularly across Europe and the Americas. Expanding international collaboration and engaging with global research networks could enhance Asia's visibility and citation impact. Relying solely on Scopus data, this study may exclude relevant literature not indexed in Scopus. This study, despite the limitations of using Scopus, emphasizes the growing importance of Asian countries in the field. These insights shed light on the evolving GCE landscape, showcasing the significant contributions of Asian nations and helping researchers, policymakers, and educators understand emerging and pivotal topics across global contexts. **Conclusion:** This study highlights the growing importance of Asian contributions to GCE research and provides a comparative analysis with global trends. It underscores the need for increased international collaboration and integration of regional perspectives to enhance GCE research and practice. The differences in focus suggest opportunities for cross-regional knowledge exchange and cooperation. Policymakers, educators, and researchers can leverage these insights to address global citizenship education challenges and foster a more inclusive and comprehensive understanding of GCE.

Keywords: Global competencies, regional variations, scientometrics

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